

Geosciences Open Science Ecosystem (GEO OSE) 2026 PI Meeting Report

Overview

The GEO OSE 2026 PI Meeting took place at the American Geophysical Union's Office in Washington D.C. over two full days from April 30 - May 1. Twenty-six principal investigators from sixteen GEO OSE Program awards participated in the meeting's expository and interactive programming. The GEO OSE project GeoFAIR hosted the meeting with NSF Program Managers and other federal agency leaders to update participants on relevant Open Science ecosystem topics. Participants began by collaboratively refining elements of a vibrant Open Science ecosystem, given a set of seed elements provided by the meeting chairs. They were asked to consider their project goals and objectives and think critically about how they fit into the concept of the co-determined Open Science ecosystem components. This was achieved through an interactive component, called the "Bird House" activity, considering which elements of a thriving open science ecosystem are represented by the projects and where there are gaps. This Bird House activity included a poster session, short presentations to small groups of participants, and anonymous mapping on the Open Science topics covered by each GEO OSE grantee project. Participants enjoyed the activity, made meaningful connections with other projects, and considered ways to mitigate identified Open Science gaps.

Objectives for the meeting

The meeting's main objective was to provide an important opportunity for GEO OSE PI's to share their project objectives and ongoing outcomes and to discover synergies between other projects, thereby increasing the reach and impact of the GEO OSE program. In addition, project leads were charged with collectively considering the component elements of open science to co-construct a shared vision for a thriving open science ecosystem, map current GEO OSE project to these elements, and think critically about gaps and future research and educational needs. Meeting activities were explicitly designed to leverage open science techniques (for example, co-designing elements of a thriving OS ecosystem) and were aimed at elevating the impact of each project's contribution toward advancing the practice of open geoscience. The design of the meeting was intended to connect the work of each GEO OSE PI team to the broader elements of Open Science, focusing on cross-team awareness, as well as identifying and nurturing potential collaboration opportunities. To further optimize impact, the chairs included current global initiatives hosted by RDA and ESIP (including contact information) that align with the meeting topics presented, facilitating the program's reach and potential for global engagement, and helping to advance the practice of open science within the global geoscience research community.

Agenda

The first day opened with brief introductory remarks from meeting hosts and Raleigh Martin, Program Officer for the GEO-OSE program. Participants broke into five breakout groups and

worked to identify and discuss elements of the open science ecosystem, reporting out in a plenary discussion. Six open science ecosystem elements were “seeded” for discussion:

- **Training and Education:** workshops, curricula, skill-building
- **Community and Governance:** building networks, cohorts, shared visions
- **Infrastructure and Tools:** data systems, software, disciplinary workflows
- **Interoperability and Standards:** formats, metadata, persistent identifiers
- **Sustainability:** long-term funding, cost-recovery, institutional support, leadership cultivation
- **Adoption, Incentives, Impact:** motivating uptake and measuring impact

Bird Color Key Chart

Breakout groups reported back and the group engaged in plenary discussion, deciding to modify the six open science ecosystem elements as follows:

- **Training and Education:** workshops, curricula, skill-building
- **Community and Governance:** building networks, cohorts, shared visions
- **Infrastructure and Tools, Access:** data systems, software, disciplinary workflows, accessibility
- **Interoperability and Standards:** formats, metadata, persistent identifiers
- **Sustainability, Operational Metrics:** long-term funding, cost-recovery, institutional support, leadership cultivation, [engagement measurement](#)
- **Adoption, Incentives, Impact, Ethics, Recognition/Contribution, Inclusive:** motivating uptake and measuring impact, [data ownership and sovereignty](#), [credit for contribution](#), [robust provenance tracking](#)
- **Additional Considerations**
 - + Recognition / Credit / Contribution / Protection of the value of Open Science contributions
 - + Trust
 - + Valuation
 - + Provenance that recognizes Open Science tools used. “Spotify Wrap”
 - + Metrics (e.g., use, engagement)

A poster session and “birdhouse activity” concluded the morning session: all GEO-OSE PIs prepared a modified NSF quad chart in advance of the meeting (meeting hosts provided a template) and placed these around the room. The poster session was broken into four micro-sessions. For each micro-session, participants rotated through

four, four-minute lightning talks. As part of the “birdhouse activity,” participants picked up small paper-punched birds consisting of six different colors keyed to the open science ecosystem elements. After each lightning talk, participants placed birds corresponding to the open science ecosystem elements they associated with each project into a small wooden birdhouse affixed next to each poster.

After lunch, an NSF panel (Raleigh Martin, Jemin George, Plato Smith) shared updates and information from GEO, TIP, and OAC/FAIROS. The remainder of the afternoon was spent back in breakout groups - meeting participants created “bird charts” for each poster to create a visual representation of the results.

The second day opened with a brief recap by meeting hosts of Day 1 and overview of Day 2, followed by a panel featuring cross-agency perspectives and additional related external initiatives (Christopher Marcum, Joe Fillingham, Katie Baynes). In response to the evolution of the discussion from Day 1, the latter half of the morning involved a full plenary discussion on continued reflections and outcomes (instead of breakout groups and report backs as initially planned). The discussion was rich and is further captured in the meeting notes. After lunch, an “Emerging Topics” session led by Shelley Stall provided an opportunity for the GEO OSE cohort to learn about ongoing OSE-related initiatives occurring at AGU, through the Research Data Alliance, and other communities in the open science ecosystem. See Appendix A for full agenda.

Summary

As hosts of the meeting, we believe the meeting objectives were fully met. The tone in the room was buoyant as everyone felt comfortable making “bird” puns and analogies. Juxtaposed with the humor was intense cross-project understanding and analysis using the Open Science Ecosystem elements. Each group presented a 4-min project briefing to four or five groups, and attended all presentations. This was a significant cognitive load. The benefit was deemed by the survey responses as “useful” and “valuable”. We were all able to have deeper insight into our roles in the Open Science ecosystem and new opportunities to connect now or in future work.

Overall, each project’s Bird House had a substantial “number of birds”, with strong distribution across five of the six Open Science Ecosystem elements. Project #4’s “bird chart” is shown here as an example. Several projects demonstrated their creativity in drawing “bird charts.”

The one Open Science Ecosystem element where most projects had “a small flock” was “sustainability” (yellow birds). Some projects felt it was a matter of tuning their project’s 4-minute pitch to highlight that information more, while others focused more on innovation and less on sustainment by nature of the design of their project. No matter the situation with each project, the topic of sustainability, in general, is challenging. This also came out

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on the survey (Appendix C) results as a focus for future meetings. The bar chart below is the “Summary Bird Chart” with all birds aggregated from all posters plotted across each element.

As a cohort, the topic of sustainability as well as those identified in survey feedback in Appendix B would be excellent to explore more deeply.

Our panel for the first day included NSF representatives from different directorates that are complementary to the scope of GEO OSE. Raleigh Martin, the Program Officer for GEO OSE, shared history from the EarthCube program, FAIROS, and then the launch of GEO OSE in 2023. He shared the innovative news about the improved form for the Data Management

Sharing plan rolling out on 27 April 2026. Plato Smith, representing OAC/FAIROS, shared the current status on FAIROS and that they had received over 97 proposals in the most recent FAIROS solicitation (April 2026). Jemin George from the TIP/Open Knowledge Network rounded out the panel with an updated status on the 41 federated knowledge graphs and challenged the project teams in the room to consider reviewing the six Proto-OKN graphs that were aligned with the geosciences and determine how data, identifiers, or users could be integrated.

Summary Bird Chart

Notable statements from the Q&A included:

- Anticipate fewer and more open-ended funding opportunities going forward at NSF - in general.
- AI and quantum-focused opportunities
- Question about knowledge graphs and knowledge graph production - intersections, challenges with international partners
 - Europe more developed in knowledge graph production (vs. U.S. slightly more focused on ML applications)
 - Emphasize that Knowledge Graphs and Machine Learning are complimentary approaches (see LLM + KN data from the slides)
- NSF has $\frac{1}{3}$ less staff now than a year ago

As we closed up the first day, one of our participants remarked on the usefulness of the day’s activities, offering a quote from John Dewey: “We do not learn from experience, we learn from reflecting on experience.”

The second day started with a panel “Federal Cross-Agency and Friends, Perspectives.” Chris Marcum led the panel with a talk titled “Developing a Strategic Plan for the Coalition for Resilient Research Data Infrastructure” reflecting on his experience at OSTP working on Open Science related efforts and reflecting on the question of “How do we enable a more resilient research data ecosystem that is resistant to single points of failure?” being embraced by the Center for Open Science on a project funded by the Robert Wood Johnson Foundation. Joe Fillingham, NOAA Data Governance Lead and Assistant Chief Data Officer, shared NOAA’s Open Data Policy Framework. Joe shared the work on building a culture of openness early and often and that the culture of openness is a component of the open science ecosystem. NOAA is helping

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Danie Kinkade welcoming everyone back to the second day. The panel is in place: Joe Fillingham, Chris Marcum, Katie Baynes

“reframe the drudgery of data management.” The final member of the panel was Katie Baynes, NASA’s Earth Data Officer. Her talk on “Earth Data Perspectives on Open Science” shared relevant resources:

- NASA Earthdata Learning Resources:
<https://www.earthdata.nasa.gov/learn>
- Openscapes:
<https://openscapes.org/>

She also shared a motivating quote, “Proceeding until apprehended.” This is applied to gaps between policy and application of open data / open science. In short, for communities where it is possible, proceed in applying open science practices when policy is not in place, or ambiguous.

The full room on the second day

Following the talks by the panel we continued plenary discussion reflecting on the Open Science ecosystem six elements and discussed how to make meaningful progress. Reflections and outcomes included:

- Discussion on not seeing ourselves in iCorps - missing a bridge between traditional business canvas/business model development and the unique challenges and value propositions of open science infrastructure
- Having more guidance on ways to collect and transfer money within the realities of university-born or university-hosted open science infrastructure projects

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- Making cyberinfrastructure that is low-maintenance as its own form of sustainability - asking proposers early on about how they are going to create software that is stable; so that updates don't cause failure
- How important it is to credit contributors even when you don't have a traditional citable unit and the pressing need for change with respect to promotion and tenure and community incentives in order to align with FAIR and/or open science foci from funders and publishers

During the meeting, several topics for better understanding were requested related to the work happening in the AGU Open Science Leadership team. Shelley Stall re-worked the originally planned presentation on "Open Science for Teams" to provide that information. Admittedly, it was an extended and content-heavy presentation at the end of an already robust discussions, with the benefit of bringing a critical group of Open Science experts up-to-date on relevant topics very quickly. Slides with resource information are in Appendix E.

As the second day concluded, during the final wrap up we reflected on the premise that Open Science depends on contributions made during the research lifecycle and must be recognized. At the moment it is unclear how the concept of "credit" can be applied beyond peer-reviewed publication. A topic for next time.

Appendices

Appendix A: Full Agenda

Day One: 8:30am-5:00pm	
7:30 - 8:30	Breakfast
8:30 - 9:00 am	Welcome & Housekeeping <i>Mountain View-Volcano 113B&C</i>
9:00 - 10:00 am	Breakout Groups: What is the Open Science Ecosystem?
10:00 - 10:30 am	Report Outs: Building a shared vision of the Open Science Ecosystem (OSE) Elements
<i>Break (15 minutes)</i>	
10:45 am - 12:00 pm	Poster Session for GEO OSE projects (4 timed groups using poster template; OSE Element Identification (Birdhouse Activity))
<i>Lunch (12:00 - 1:30 pm)</i>	
<i>AGU NetZero Building Tour (optional) - meet in the lobby at 12:45, returning 1:30pm</i>	
1:30 pm - 3:00 pm	Panel: NSF Focused - Federal cross-agency perspectives (~3 ten-minute presentations + discussion) Presenters: Raleigh Martin - Geosciences Jemin George - TIP Directorate; Open Knowledge Network Plato Smith - OAC; FAIROS
<i>Break (15 minutes)</i>	
3:15 pm - 4:00 pm	Breakout Groups (~4 posters per group): summarize the birdhouses Open Science Ecosystem
<i>Break (5 minutes)</i>	
4:05pm - 4:45 pm	Reports and Synthesis of Birdhouse Activity
4:45 pm - 5:00 pm	Wrap-up
<i>Adjourn</i>	
Day Two: 8:30am-4:30pm	
7:30 - 8:30	Breakfast
8:30-9:00 am	Welcome Back (Summarize Day One, Outcomes from OSE Breakout Groups) <i>Mountain View-Volcano 113B&C</i>
9:00 - 10:15 am	Panel: Federal cross-agency, and friends, perspectives (~3 ten-minute presentations + discussion) Presenters: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Christopher Marcum (Data Foundation, previous OMB, OSTP) - Confirmed ● Joseph Fillingham (NOAA) - Confirmed ● Katie Baynes (NASA) - Confirmed
<i>Break (15 minutes)</i>	
10:30 am - 12:00 pm	Plenary Discussion: Reflections and Outcomes
<i>Lunch (12:00 - 1:30 pm)</i>	

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1:30 pm - 3:00 pm	Talk/Discussion: Emerging Topics (Shelley Stall) + 3-question feedback: http://bit.ly/4cJAxGK
<i>Break (10 minutes)</i>	
3:10 pm - 4:00 pm	Final Closing Discussion
<i>Adjourn</i>	

Appendix B: Topics for Additional Exploration in future workshops

1. Citation / Digital Object Citation
2. "Credit"
 - a. How to recognize use and/or value
 - b. Ensuring that AI provides provenance and credit
3. Developing an Open Science Community
4. Understanding and leveraging Knowledge Graphs
5. Systems thinking updates that provide value across the ecosystem
6. How is the Open Science Ecosystem evolving within the context of generative AI (LLMs)?
 - a. No one "codes" any more – therefore attribution of building code is now different;
 - i. PLUS: labor costs of developing and maintaining functional code are drastically lower.
 - ii. MINUS: sorting through the tide of agentic contributions (can agents police agents? Or is there still a human bottleneck to code design).
 - b. Adoption bottleneck: LLMs only recommends the most popular solutions and likes to re-invent the wheel. Solution: an OSE knowledge graph to keep LLMs on geo rails?
 - c. Unequal access to AI (e.g. institutional subscriptions or not); cannot be taken for granted. Could widen the gap between "farm to table" human contributions and agentic contributions (e.g. continuous integration tests, which AI is very good at)
 - d. AI science agents are there (e.g. [PaleoPAL](#)). How should they be acknowledged in publications?
7. Society recognition of Open Science practices
8. Adoption of open practices, codes, methods
 - a. "Practice is the product" – how can it be measured, other than anecdotally?
9. Sustainability -
 - a. Who are the stakeholders
 - b. What should be sustained, and how design good management
10. Intentional digitization of "legacy" data
11. Recognition
 - a. For software / data contributions as part of the scientific record, and thus needing to value this contribution, and supporting a career
12. Training
 - a. Where to find quality, trusted training on Open Science

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Appendix C: Survey Results

The short survey was taken halfway through the second day with the intent on capturing feedback before participants started to leave later that day. There were 15 responses.

Coming out of the meeting, summarize your impressions in one word.	What was most valuable about this meeting?	What's one change that would make the next GEO-OSE PI meeting more valuable to your work?
Impressed	The metacognition of what constitutes open science	Examples / discussions of actual implementation of open science projects
Excellent	Opportunity to reflect and compare with other OSE project and see how they overlap/intersect/support one another.	Targeted final vision/outcome objective from the beginning of the meeting. What is the culminating activity (if there is one).
Thoughtful	Cogitating with other like-minded people with deep expertise and relevant experience	Training us to better sell our open science resources to ensure sustainability!
Hopeful	The bird-voting was both fun and helped uncover some interesting cross-project themes and challenges. Well done!	Another round of GEO-OSE funding!
Useful	Bird house activities were super insightful and a good use of time.	This has been the best meeting of its type I have ever attended. Great job y'all!
Intriguing	Meeting people I can collaborate with and learn from.	Include some activities towards sustainability -- business mentoring or consultation, meetings with funders (e.g. reps from industry, foundations, local governments...) .
Motivating & scary? (Sorry, 2 words)	It was really great to meet other PIs and hear about other open science projects. Was a good way to think about collaborations.	I felt like there was too much time spent on the same topic- the 6 categories of open science. By day 2 our group agreed we would've liked to discuss something else, maybe something more forward-thinking?
Keeping doing open science	Connections.	Hands-on workshop on a specific tool. E.g. how to make knowledge graphs.

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Coming out of the meeting, summarize your impressions in one word.	What was most valuable about this meeting?	What's one change that would make the next GEO-OSE PI meeting more valuable to your work?
Connected	Learning from people solving similar problems in different organizational contexts	More specific interactions and feedback from NSF program staff.
Positive	The speaker panels were really useful. This is not to de-emphasize the usefulness of collaboration and discussion with other teams, but being able to get the thoughts of Program Managers and agency leaders in a smaller setting is really really useful.	Day 1 had a LOT of cognitive load. I wonder if we could even that out a little more over the two days.
Valuation	Liked hearing about key elements from other projects (though there wasn't quite enough time to digest - glad there are notes!) Some of the talks were especially informative, while others didn't share anything new. Time to talk directly to people both in structured time and in breaks and meals.	Would be interested in mapping across projects on infrastructure, tools, functions, etc. as a means of identifying collaboration and learning points.
Collaborative	Brainstorming shared thinking and approaches to working within elements of the OSE. It's really interesting to know what working in this space means to others coming from different sub-disciplines or different types of projects. Also, identifying how projects relate to each other and finding opportunities for collaboration.	I liked this style of meeting a lot. It made it more than a typical report out and encouraged a broader vision. It could be interesting to try pitching questions from our projects that we want feedback on from the group as a next phase to build on what we did here. It was also nice to have easy meals together!
Reflection	This meeting facilitated our project's ability to reflect on its OSE goals informed both by the framing of OSE elements provided by the workshop leads and by the expertise of other GEO-OSE PIs. These science communication and sharing activities were facilitated very effectively by tapping into our cognitive, affective, and psychomotor learning pathways!	There are so many acronyms in the agency and open science space! A primer of acronyms would be invaluable!
AI is changing the open science ecosystem	Interactions with program managers and other PIs.	Nothing. This was an awesome meeting!

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Coming out of the meeting, summarize your impressions in one word.	What was most valuable about this meeting?	What's one change that would make the next GEO-OSE PI meeting more valuable to your work?
Motivated	Learn about new tools, opportunities for research, and having a space to think about the upcoming challenges in the field.	More conversations about the impact of AI in open science. For example, what AI tools can we start testing for tackling some of the open science challenges. Or how can we suggest strategies to make AI more aligned with the open science values.

Appendix D: Participant List

GEO OSE 2026 PI Meeting Attendees

GEO OSE Project Personnel (26)

Name	Affiliation	GEO-OSE Project
Andy Aschwanden	University of Alaska Fairbanks	Enhancing usability of the Parallel Ice Sheet Model (PISM) to accelerate innovative sea-level research
Bahareh Nojabaei	Virginia Tech	Digital Porous Media Portal
Bradley Cramer	University of Iowa	Toward an open science Geologic Time Scale
Brian Rose	University at Albany	
Christopher Tessum	University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign	
Danie Kinkade	Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution IN	GeoFAIR
Daven Quinn	UW–Madison	Macrostrat–StraboSpot integration
David Hyde	Vanderbilt University	Adviser
Drew Davidson	University of Kansas	StraboSpot Collaborative Workflows
Einat Lev	Columbia University	VICTOR
Enrique Rojas Villalba	MIT	
Gelu Nita	New Jersey Institute of Technology	
Holly Little	Smithsonian Institution	Community-driven enhancement of information ecosystems for the discovery and use of paleontological specimen data
Jim Colliander	2i2c	
John Clyne	NCAR	
Julien Emile-Geay	University of Southern California	

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Name	Affiliation	GEO-OSE Project
Andy Aschwanden	University of Alaska Fairbanks	Enhancing usability of the Parallel Ice Sheet Model (PISM) to accelerate innovative sea-level research
Lei Zhao	University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign	
Mark Schmitz	Boise State University	Toward an open science Geologic Time Scale
Masa Prodanovic	UT Austin	Digital Porous Media Portal
Mickey MacKie	University of Florida	
Natalie Raia	University of Arizona	GeoFAIR
Nicole Greco	UC Santa Barbara/NCEAS	Arctic Data Center & QGreenland Net
Robin Trayler	UC-Merced	Toward an open science Geologic Time Scale
Shelley Stall	American Geophysical Union	GeoFAIR
Twila Moon	University of Colorado Boulder	QGreenland-Net

Guest Speakers and Additional Participants (9)

Name	Affiliation
Chris Marcum	Data Foundation
Jemin George	NSF
Joe Fillingham	NOAA
Katie Baynes	NASA
Lisa-Joy Zgorski	NSF OISE
Yurena Yanes	NSF
Plato Smith	NSF
Raleigh Martin	NSF
Marlon Pierce	NSF

Appendix E: Links to Slide Presentations

Full Meeting Slides:

https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1JpaVApDKRjyg1ihWWyG-uF0HdQbMb3U__nVey-66s-w/edit?usp=sharing

Collaborative Meeting Notes:

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1RzLk2ksnAPn1KAym5IUoHaTb-lqI0WfNI16C9DQ6kwU/edit?tab=t.8w2jpr41d1t6>

NSF Speakers:

Martin:

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1Uhk_tsX2Cd9NxKMPNTEfBrW_klz78v2/view?usp=drive_link

Smith:

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1CtCMFiknSJ4OZfiAaBeGnyqJQq5eB9e2/view?usp=drive_link

George: https://drive.google.com/file/d/10Tq2hn4D5x1tc4O-LI9LG6V5urDYHEro/view?usp=drive_link

Additional Federal Partner Speakers:

Marcum:

<https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1G85n1Z0RBmM2HtxkDjDGL1FWmxGoJTVNuMIWdw2X7j4/edit?usp=sharing>

Fillingham: https://drive.google.com/file/d/15Az1tkuTIIRT9W1cuFFfhGBLwHKi-M0B/view?usp=drive_link

Baynes:

https://drive.google.com/file/d/11XywpMQCu8UgSuTuAcFCmm8bBnINqEwR/view?usp=drive_link

AGU Open Science and related activities:

Stall:

https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1s3ZNj1GDz2uUUvLeanTVPE4hkkJKqt-m/edit?usp=drive_link&oid=111553763686023640655&rtpof=true&sd=true